

The need to take into account the impact of sanctions restrictions when conducting marketing research in order to strategic development of enterprises

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Аннотация. В статье рассмотрено воздействие санкционных ограничений на развитие экономики страны, а также возникшие проблемы в деятельности промышленных предприятий. Проведен их краткий анализ и выявлены внутренние источники стратегического развития промышленных предприятий. Обоснована необходимость учета особенностей влияния санкционных ограничений и других факторов внешней нестабильности при формировании маркетинговых стратегий развития предприятий. Даны рекомендации по адаптации предприятий к новым экономическим условиям. Они могут быть использованы при разработке стратегий развития промышленных предприятий на основе проведения маркетинговых исследований.

Abstract. The article examines the impact of sanctions restrictions on the development of the country's economy, as well as the problems that have arisen in the activities of industrial enterprises. A brief analysis of them was carried out and internal sources of strategic development of industrial enterprises were identified. The necessity of taking into account the specific influence of sanctions restrictions and other factors of external instability when forming marketing strategies for the development of enterprises is substantiated. Recommendations are given for adapting enterprises to new economic conditions. They can be used in developing strategies for the development of industrial enterprises based on marketing research.

Ключевые слова: *российская экономика, санкционные ограничения, развитие, промышленные предприятия, стратегическое планирование, маркетинговые стратегии.*

Keywords: *Russian economy, sanctions restrictions, development, industrial enterprises, strategic planning, marketing strategies.*

Introduction.

Modern operating conditions for domestic enterprises are characterized by a high level of competition and uncertainty. That is why every business entity strives to formulate a strategy for its development, taking into account as much as possible the possible influence of environmental factors. In this regard, the identification of promising directions for the strategic development of enterprises and the development of marketing strategies for their development are of great importance.

The need for strategic management of the activities of industrial enterprises became especially acute at the beginning of the 21st century, when the need clearly arose to distinguish between the current management of production activities and development management at the strategic level. This is due to significant changes in the global economy, such as the expansion of the spheres of activity of national economies, the increasing frequency and deepening of the consequences of crisis phenomena, as well as its transition to new technological structures - the knowledge economy, information and digital economy - in response to the global challenges of the development of the world community. These changes have led to a change in the main focus of strategic management of enterprises in modern conditions. It becomes necessary to quickly respond not only to changes in the influence of ex-

ternal factors, but also to link them with issues of increasing the internal efficiency of individual enterprises or industries.

Purpose of the study.

The purpose of the article is to study the impact of sanctions restrictions on the Russian economy and its industrial enterprises, analyze problems and search for internal sources of their development. To achieve this goal, the following tasks were consistently solved: an analysis of the impact of sanctions restrictions on the development of the Russian economy and its industrial enterprises was carried out; the problems of strategic development of industrial enterprises under the influence of sanctions restrictions, possible sources of growth, prospects for the formation of development strategies based on the use of marketing tools are identified.

Since the external conditions for the activities of industrial enterprises under the influence of sanctions restrictions have become significantly more complicated, the issues of their development and management based on effective marketing strategies are of particular importance. Some approaches to solving them will be discussed in this article.

1. Negative impact of sanctions restrictions on the development of the Russian economy.

The global experience of introducing sanctions restrictions directed against the economies of

individual states clearly shows that regardless of the place of these economies in the world system, the structure of a particular market quickly adapts to new conditions through the process of reorienting the interactions of enterprises. A similar situation is now occurring in the Russian economy. We will show what it is and justify possible directions for reducing the negative impact of sanctions restrictions on the development of leading sectors of the economy of our country.

The most significant negative consequences of the introduction of new sanctions restrictions may be for the Russian banking system. Limiting the terms for attracting foreign loans and banning certain transactions have a significant impact on maintaining the liquidity of the entire banking system. After the tightening of the secondary sanctions regime at the end of 2023, banks in friendly countries sharply increased the number of refusals to make payments related to Russia. Today, more than 40 Russian banks are subject to SDN sanctions, which is 90% of bank capital. The number of foreign banks that are ready to continue working with domestic banks and enterprises is constantly decreasing. Payment terms are increasing, fees are growing, the volume of requested documentation has increased, especially for critical product groups - electronics, computers, high-precision machines and equipment. Just a year ago, when making cross-border payments, banks were faced with the task of simply excluding banks under SDN sanctions from the chain of settlement routes and not using SWIFT, but now geography itself is becoming the central problem, that is, the destination of Russia immediately creates problems for settlements. As soon as the goods go to Russia or from us, the "stop" light comes on, regardless of the loyalty of a particular bank or jurisdiction, or the sanction status of the Russian participant in the transaction [1].

At the same time, the negative impact of sanctions restrictions on the banking system in terms of attracting foreign credit resources can be significantly weakened, provided that domestic banks and the enterprises they lend to can reorient their policy in terms of obtaining loans to interact with the financial markets of other countries. With this formulation of the question, the most promising option for the Russian banking system may be interaction with the Chinese financial market, as well as with the financial markets of large countries in Asia (China, India) and Latin America (Brazil).

The effect of the negative impact of sanctions restrictions on the raw materials, mining, processing and engineering sectors of Russian industry is characterized by a number of long-term factors. Their actual manifestation may be felt after a certain period of time. In most cases, it all comes down to the specific significant impact of sanctions restrictions on individual Russian industrial corporations and enterprises in leading industries in terms of restriction or complete lack of access to certain

equipment, components and technologies [2]. First of all, this affects key sectors of the Russian mining industry – oil and gas production. It is no secret that when exploring and exploiting fields, Russian companies often use the services of foreign partners for drilling and production of hydrocarbons.

After the start of Russia's military special operation in Ukraine, the United States and European countries introduced a number of new sanctions against the Russian military-industrial complex (MIC). They affected primarily such large Russian defense concerns as air defense Almaz-Antey, Sirius, Stankoinstrument, Kalashnikov, Tula Arms Plant, NPO Eastern Complexes, as well as Dobrolet airlines. The ban on debt financing affected such major defense industry enterprises as Uralvagonzavod, Oboronprom, and United Aircraft Corporation. In this regard, a number of contracts are being postponed; there are problems with the shortage of marine diesel engines, import substitution of helicopter and aircraft engines, electronics, replacement of imported components in tank fire control systems, as well as with aircraft repairs. At the same time, all leading enterprises of the Russian defense industry continue to strictly fulfill the state defense order.

As part of the new sanctions restrictions, the United States intends to ban the sale of weapons and military equipment (WME) and dual-use technologies to organizations and individuals supporting enterprises of the Russian defense industry, limiting the supply chain of components for their needs. At the same time, all types of activities of Russian defense industry enterprises related to the development and production of all types of high-tech weapons are prohibited. The new sanctions will affect those organizations that the United States deems involved in the sale, loan or otherwise provision of dual-use components, services and technologies, as well as significant transactions with any organizations and individuals involved in the activities of Russian defense industry enterprises.

The new sanctions, first of all, significantly limited the renewal of the machine tool fleet, since Russia is not yet able to produce a significant part of the machine equipment on its own. Before the introduction of new sanctions restrictions, enterprises of the Russian defense industry purchased machine tools that were produced in the USA or in other countries, but using American technologies. Therefore, new sanctions restrictions are quite capable of creating a fairly significant problem in terms of limiting the access of Russian defense industry enterprises to the purchase of modern machine tools [3].

Another problem may be the purchase of software, since the development of all types of modern weapons and military equipment has long used special software produced mainly in the United States or other countries dependent on the United States. Naturally, companies in the United States and countries dependent on them, which have large

shares in the software market, fearing the introduction of sanctions, will prefer to sell the software being developed to other countries and will refuse to sell it to enterprises of the Russian defense industry [4].

An analysis of the impact of sanctions restrictions taking into account the scale of the Russian economy allows us to conclude that it is impossible to isolate Russia from the system of international economic relations, since it has a significant raw material base and a number of strategic raw materials that are mined only on its territory [5]. However, the idea of developing a resource-based economy has completely outlived its usefulness, and the availability of significant volumes of raw materials has long ceased to be a determining factor in economic growth. Rather, on the contrary, the leaders of economic growth around the world are predominantly those countries whose reserves of their own resources are significantly limited or absent altogether.

2. Problems and forecasts for the strategic development of enterprises under sanctions.

In the context of the negative impact of sanctions restrictions at the level of management of production activities of industrial enterprises, the problem of management efficiency, primarily in terms of strategic development, has become especially acute. Today, an increasing number of Russian industrial enterprises are striving to use advanced technologies and development strategies to manage their economic activities. But at the same time, only a small part (no more than 6-9%) of enterprises manage their production activities on the basis of clearly developed development strategies [6]. This situation can be explained by a number of reasons of a very different nature, namely:

1) the management of a number of enterprises entrusted the development of strategy to specialized consulting agencies and other structures that do not fully understand the internal and external conditions and features of their business activities;

2) the weak participation of enterprise management in the development of development strategies leads to the fact that they are not ready to change and adjust its goals and objectives depending on the impact of new internal and/or external conditions affecting their economic activities;

3) as a rule, the management of most enterprises is insufficiently responsible for management decisions and the results of the current activities of the enterprise;

4) the quality of information support and the reliability of the information used to develop strategies is not high enough, which entails inadequate assessments on the part of management of the current situation of the enterprise, as well as possible difficulties with the practical implementation of the developed strategies for the development of the enterprise.

The negative impact of sanctions restrictions has confronted most Russian industrial enterprises with the need to search for new internal and external sources to support their economic activities in terms of financial resources, introduction of innovations, technological modernization of production and restructuring of management activities, and selection of promising directions for strategic development. In other words, the introduction of sanctions restrictions and the high degree of instability of other environmental factors has become a significant problem for many enterprises, the solution of which in a short time is impossible without the development and implementation of development strategies at enterprises, as well as the effective use within their framework of marketing tools for creating competitive advantages of their products. their products [7].

Enterprises cannot completely eliminate the negative impact of external factors such as sanctions restrictions on their economic activities. Therefore, for their strategic development, increasing the efficiency of using the marketing tools of strategic management is of paramount importance. Let us present below a brief description of the main internal sources used in developing marketing strategies for enterprise development.

First of all, these are sources of finance. Industrial enterprises can obtain additional financial resources by consistently reducing the cost of their products. This approach will contribute to a more effective implementation of pricing policy, when a reasonable price reduction while maintaining the functional properties and quality characteristics of the product will increase market demand for it from potential consumers. Its result may be an increase in the enterprise's income and the possibility of using part of it to modernize fixed assets.

Modernization of an enterprise's fixed assets can be considered as a source of introducing innovative technologies into production. Subject to modernization of production and its technological renewal based on the introduction of innovative developments, an enterprise can gain real competitive advantages not only in relation to other enterprises in the industry, but also in relation to competitors in foreign markets for its products. That is why this internal source of strategic development of the enterprise should be used wisely at all stages of the life cycle of specific types of products. It is also necessary to systematically monitor the qualitative indicators of the enterprise's economic performance with similar indicators of its main competitors.

Modernization will increase the efficiency of using fixed assets and will have a significant impact on the growth of production. This will allow many enterprises to replace obsolete equipment with more modern domestic or foreign analogues from countries that have not imposed sanctions restrictions on the Russian economy. A similar ap-

proach can be used in relation to materials, components, equipment and technologies that are used in the production activities of enterprises.

In modern conditions, the possession of information resources becomes the most important source for the formation of marketing strategies for the development of an enterprise. They combined socio-economic, scientific, innovative and other types of knowledge and their information representation in relevant technologies. The ability of the enterprise management to use them efficiently, effectively and in a timely manner will largely determine whether the enterprise has a competitive advantage.

The introduction of sanctions restrictions resulted in the emergence of problems for some enterprises in providing their economic activities with all types of necessary resources. As is known, the availability of resources is of decisive importance for the conduct of production activities, since the existence of an enterprise as an independent economic entity completely depends on it. Therefore, under the conditions of sanctions restrictions, almost every enterprise is forced to reconsider the possibilities of maintaining the previous supply of resources and the loyalty of all counterparties to it.

Another important internal source of strategic development of an enterprise can be improving the

quality of production of all types of products it produces. Naturally, this source can play its role only if most of the above internal sources for ensuring the strategic development of the enterprise are available and correctly implemented in practice.

Since all of the above internal sources are interconnected, their joint use will have a more tangible positive effect. Features of the use of internal sources of strategic development in the context of the negative impact of sanctions restrictions are shown in the table below.

The analysis showed that the development of industrial production depends on the influence of many factors of the internal and external environment, which have a multidirectional impact on the activities of enterprises.

The development of strategies for the development of enterprises in the context of the negative impact of sanctions restrictions consists of the simultaneous formation of a number of options that take into account both the deterioration and stabilization and possible improvement of the impact of internal and external factors on their economic activities. At the same time, it is advisable to consider, first of all, the internal sources of the enterprise as prospects for strategic development. This will minimize any dependence on the influence of external factors, such as sanctions restrictions [8].

Table 1

The use of external and internal sources for the strategic development of enterprises under the influence of external and internal factors

Negative impact of sanctions restrictions	Directions for using internal sources for strategic development
External	
Prohibition on attracting external sources of financing	Participation in programs and projects with government support and preferential lending conditions; Formation of new sources of attracting finance; Use of the enterprise's own funds
Reduced market demand	Reducing the cost of production and increasing its quality through modernization of production; Development of development strategies using marketing research tools and internal sources
Limiting access to innovation	Increasing the level of innovation implementation through rapid modernization of fixed assets
Prohibition of supplies	Use of domestic and foreign (from countries that have not imposed sanctions restrictions) high-tech materials, components, equipment and technologies
Breach of previous business relationships	Search for new counterparties in countries that have not imposed sanctions restrictions
Internal	
Low management efficiency	Participation of management in the development of development strategies; Changing development goals and objectives depending on the action of external factors; Improving management training
Low responsibility	Introduction of financial responsibility for decisions made; Improving management training
Low quality, use of false information	Development and implementation of a quality management system; Optimization of the document flow system; Using only verified information; Ensuring information protection of the enterprise management system
Increased level of depreciation of fixed assets	Using internal sources for modernization and technological renewal of production; Use of domestically produced equipment
Rising costs, rising prices for raw materials	Introduction of high-tech equipment; Improving the quality of production and personnel qualifications; Search for new suppliers of raw materials used

According to some experts, the negative impact of sanctions restrictions will most likely have a significant impact on the financial and investment sectors. Thus, a ban on the export of high-tech equipment may increase the implementation time of certain investment projects with the joint participation of foreign counterparties. At the same time, the implementation time of such projects may increase

due to a reduction in global demand and a decrease in world prices for hydrocarbons. At the same time, the ban on attracting new medium- and long-term financial resources will entail a reduction in external financial investments in new investment assets.

Taking into account the above circumstances, it becomes relevant to develop and implement development strategies for industrial enterprises,

which will not only ensure their existence as independent economic entities, but also strategic development based on internal sources [9]. With regard to industrial enterprises, the greatest economic effect comes from their economic activities in the production of various types of products. At the same time, the production activities of the enterprise are interconnected with other types of its activities that accompany the main production: financial and resource support, the availability of fixed assets and other equipment, personnel selection activities, marketing activities, etc. On this basis, it can be argued that the development strategy of an industrial enterprise is complex in nature and is intricately connected with the main components of its internal environment. At the same time, let's not forget that the enterprise development strategy should be formed taking into account the influence of environmental factors.

Thus, in order to maintain the stable development of an enterprise under the negative influence of environmental factors, it is necessary to minimize their impact through internal sources and timely form new partnerships with both domestic manufacturers and foreign counterparties. Of particular importance is a timely response to government regulatory measures to reduce the negative impact of sanctions restrictions.

3. Marketing tools for developing development strategies.

Modern practice of leading foreign and Russian enterprises shows that the use of marketing tools has become an obligatory element in the development of development strategies [10]. Marketing tools, consisting of various methods and technologies for regulating the activities of enterprises, make it possible with a high degree of probability to predict the market reaction to the influence of environmental factors and thereby ensure timely and adequate consideration of them in the activities of the enterprise. Ultimately, its use helps maintain the sustainability of the enterprise. In conditions of growing and toughening competition, the use of marketing tools ensures the successful development of the enterprise's activities based on taking into account the peculiarities of the functioning of the market and the possibilities of strategic management of its activities.

The use of marketing tools to formulate enterprise development strategies today is becoming more important than ever. It allows you to predict the current activity of an enterprise and the prospects for its changes in the future, develop alternative options for its development strategies, and ensure the competitiveness of the enterprise in the long term. To effectively realize the potential of marketing tools when forming development strategies, enterprise management must pay attention to such issues of organizing marketing activities as: the use of marketing tools in the enterprise management

system; readiness to quickly respond to changes in the impact of environmental factors; the need to restructure activities to achieve strategic objectives; providing production with resources and promoting it to markets.

In the modern understanding, an industrial enterprise can be considered as an open socio-economic system that operates under constant changes in the influence of environmental factors and an increase in the likelihood of risks. These circumstances predetermine the need for a prompt response to these changes on the part of the enterprise in order to adapt its capabilities to market dynamics. This difficult task can be successfully solved by using strategic marketing tools. In the modern understanding, strategic marketing combines all components of an enterprise's activities, the main goal of which is to produce in-demand products and make a profit. The concept of "strategic marketing" was first used by the American company DuPont. Its management reoriented the company's activities to meet the specific needs of potential consumers in a specific market segment through marketing research [11]. The difference between the concept of "strategic marketing" and the traditional definition of marketing is that the demands of a specific consumer were put at the forefront, and not the production of in-demand products.

The concept of strategic marketing is intended to study the cumulative influence of factors in the market microenvironment of an enterprise (consumers, competitors, suppliers), on which it can have a certain influence, as well as factors in the macroenvironment (political, socio-economic, legal, technological, etc.), which the enterprise can regulate can't do it on his own. The results of the analysis of this set of factors are the basis for the formation of an enterprise development strategy, the purpose of which is to ensure its financial stability and competitiveness. To do this, it is advisable to use strategic marketing tools.

The formation of an enterprise development strategy using strategic marketing tools is carried out by justifying the goal of its development. It defines the traditional components of the marketing strategy according to the 4P Model: Product – development of product production; Price – development of pricing and maintaining competitiveness; Place – development of product promotion channels; Promotion – development of relationships with consumers and counterparties.

When forming an enterprise development strategy using strategic marketing tools, the influence of numerous factors of the external and internal environment is taken into account, which is accompanied by the need to take into account and process significant amounts of marketing information. These factors can be grouped into the following areas.

1. Study of the dynamics of supply and demand under the influence of external and internal environmental factors.

2. Study of the presence of competitors, strategies for their development and features of competition.

3. Study of the management system, resource provision, internal opportunities for the development of the enterprise.

4. Determining the goals and objectives of the enterprise in specific market segments.

With the development of markets and marketing concepts, new marketing mix models have emerged. They cover other elements of marketing that also affect customer satisfaction and sales. Below are other famous models.

In the 5P Model, one more element is added to the standard elements - "people". These are those who are involved in the product marketing process and influence consumer decision making. For example, company employees, customers, opinion leaders and point-of-sale personnel. This model emerged with the development of relationship marketing. It is mainly used to promote services.

In the 6P Model, "public relations" and "politics" were added to the elements of the 4P Model in this model. The model assumes that for successful promotion it is necessary to form public opinion and enlist the support of organizations that regulate the market.

Model 7P complements Model 5P with two more elements: "process" (process) and "physical environment" (physical evidence): process - the interaction of the consumer with the company and the physical environment - the creation of a favorable atmosphere around the consumer. The 7P model is used in services marketing and B2B niches. In B2B, the process of interaction between buyers and a company is especially important because it is usually long and consists of several stages.

Strategic marketing tools are necessary to take into account the combined influence of internal and external environmental factors. Research into the influence of factors in the internal environment of an enterprise is carried out using SWOT analysis, which allows one to determine the strengths and weaknesses, as well as opportunities and threats for the strategic development of the enterprise [12]. The results of the SWOT analysis are used to substantiate the directions of strategic development of the enterprise, as well as to determine the goals and objectives of the development of its activities. In addition, with their help, promising directions for the development of the product/market scheme are selected, taking into account possible alternatives, namely: increasing the market, increasing the share of the enterprise, developing the product range, entering new segments. The results of the SWOT analysis are used to determine the strategic goals of product development, which are transformed into

specific tasks of the enterprise, solved in specific market segments.

To study the influence of environmental factors, PEST analysis (or STEP analysis) is usually used [13]. It is intended to determine the level and direction of influence of macro-level factors that must be taken into account when forming an enterprise development strategy. This toolkit allows you to determine the causes of market dynamics over time, as well as the potential capabilities of the enterprise to adequately respond to them. Using PEST analysis tools, the four most significant groups of environmental factors are examined. Political is a group of geopolitical factors, the influence of which must be taken into account when forming an enterprise development strategy. Economic is a group of macroeconomic factors that have a cumulative impact on the development of the enterprise. Social – a group of social factors that determine the living conditions of the working population in the area where the enterprise is located. Technological is a group of factors that determine the conditions for the use of advanced innovative technologies at an enterprise.

Thanks to a large-scale systemic program for the development of the economy of a new technological generation, the so-called digital economy, the digitalization of marketing has become possible. The use of digital marketing tools can significantly reduce transaction costs associated with searching, exchanging and storing information, optimizing processes associated with the creation of goods and services, and also allows for constant feedback and the development of individual offers, increasing consumer interest in marketing programs and reduce the number of contacts with consumers. This radically improves marketing results, increases business profitability, and is very relevant during a pandemic. However, the transition to digital rails is impossible without increasing the level of digital literacy of managers and personnel of enterprises, eliminating the lack of modern technologies and equipment, developing modern digital platforms, modernizing information security standards at the enterprise level and introducing control over their implementation. Further development of digital marketing involves the development of digitalization of the economy as a whole, and then the improvement of marketing tools [14].

The above circumstances allow us to consider strategic marketing as a specific type of business activity that covers the strategic directions of development of the enterprise's activities and ensures its financial stability. Based on this, within the framework of enterprise development strategies, it is necessary to study alternative options in no less than three areas:

- attracting additional investments necessary for a prompt response to market dynamics;

- coordination of production according to volumes of resources, seasonal demand, promotion channels and other indicators;

- determination of the necessary volumes of working capital to maintain the financial liquidity of the enterprise in the long and short term.

The above information provides grounds for presenting the essence of the enterprise's development strategy through identifying promising directions for its activities and production development using strategic marketing tools. The successful operation of an enterprise is based on the consistent implementation of its development strategy through management decisions made by the management of the enterprise. At the same time, the main task of the enterprise is to respond in a timely manner to the challenges of the external environment and search for internal sources to maintain its competitiveness, financial independence and economic independence.

Conclusion.

During the research, results were obtained that provide grounds for formulating the main conclusions:

1. The consequences and effects of the introduction of sanctions restrictions will have a negative impact on the development of the Russian economy for a long time. Therefore, both at the industry level and at the level of individual enterprises, the importance of strategic planning and selection of promising directions that allow them to remain competitive in domestic and especially foreign markets is increasing.

2. Most of the enterprises in the leading spheres of the Russian economy were able to quite successfully adapt their activities to the negative impacts of external environmental factors, such as sanctions restrictions, the fall in world prices for hydrocarbons, the manifestation of the consequences of various kinds of crisis phenomena in the global economy, etc.

3. In the current conditions, domestic industrial enterprises are forced to pay close attention to the search for internal sources and reserves in order to use them for the formation and implementation of marketing strategies for the development of their activities.

4. Modern strategic marketing tools have quite a wide range of capabilities for shaping enterprise development strategies. Research into the influence of internal environmental factors is carried out using SWOT analysis tools, and research into the influence of external environmental factors is carried out using PEST analysis tools. Also, in the arsenal of modern strategic marketing today there is a representative set of other, including digital, tools for identifying and assessing the influence of external and internal environmental factors. The management of an enterprise has the right to choose

one or another tool to formulate its development strategy.

Bibliography:

1. Kostin A. War of sanctions. RBC. [Electronic resource]. Access mode: URL – <https://www.rbc.ru/finances/11/04/2024/6617cbb19a7947c8c6001f9c?ysclid=luwk5e5wxm132121802> (access date 04/12/2024).
2. Sanctions against Russia. List // AIF.RU [Electronic resource]. Access mode: URL – <http://www.aif.ru/dontknows/actual/1159761> (date of access: 04/12/2024).
3. Markov S., Polunin A., Katasonov V. New “eternal” sanctions threaten the collapse of the domestic economy [Electronic resource]. Access mode: URL – http://ruskline.ru/opp/2017/iyul/27/novye_vechnye_sankcii_grozyat_krahom_otechestvennoj_ekonomike/ (date accessed 04/12/2024).
4. Filippova I.A. The role and impact of sanctions on the Russian economy in 2022 // Fundamentals of Economics, Management and Law, 2022. No. 4(35). P.33-35. doi:10.51608/23058641_2022_4_33.
5. Drobot E.V., Makarov I.N., Ivanova A.A. Features of public management of the development of strategic industries in the context of economic sanctions: institutional and systemic aspects // Russian Entrepreneurship, 2017. Volume 18. No. 19. Pp. 2769-2786. doi: 10.18334/rp.18.19.38358.
6. Konovalov Yu.V. Mechanisms of industrial policy influencing import substitution and innovation strategy of enterprises // Russian Entrepreneurship, 2017. No. 6. Pp. 957-970. doi: 10.18334/rp.18.6.37653.
7. Marketing strategy of the organization in 2020 // Professional magazine for economists, financiers, top managers and executives. XI International Scientific and Practical Conference “MODERN TRENDS AND INNOVATIONS IN SCIENCE AND PRODUCTION” April 27-28, 2022. 251-7 economic planning departments. [Electronic resource] – URL: https://www.profiz.ru/peo/1_2020/marketingovaja_strategija/ (access date: 04/12/2024).
8. Voronova S.M., Ordynskaya O.N. Sanctions and their impact on the activities of Russian enterprises // Theory and practice of service: economics, social sphere, technology. 2022. No. 4 (54). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/sanktsii-i-ih-vliyanie-na-deyatelnostrossijskih-predpriyatij> (date of access: 04/12/2023).
9. Andreev V.D., Bokov M.A. Theory and practice of strategic planning / Ed. IN AND. Shapovalova. – Sochi: RIC SGUTiKD, 2019. – 264 p.
10. Berezina E.A. Study of the effectiveness of marketing organization in an enterprise. // SMALTA. 2018. No. 6. Pp. 18-20.
11. Efimova S.A. Marketing planning. – M.: AlfaPress Publishing House, 2020. – 122 p.
12. Luzhnova N.V., Kalieva O.M. Strategic marketing management: textbook / Orenburg State University. – Orenburg: OSU, 2017. – 288 p.
13. Arsenyeva N.V., Putyatina L.M. Marketing potential of an enterprise and the possibilities of its development in modern conditions // Bulletin of the University. 2021. No. 7. Pp. 5-11.
14. Krasnyuk I.A., Pasholikhov M.A. The influence of marketing strategy on the activities of an industrial enterprise in the context of digitalization // Practical marketing. 2021. No. 4 (290). Pp. 10-16.